

**SHAPE-DEFINED MICROPLATES FOR THE SUSTAINED INTRAARTICULAR RELEASE OF
DEXAMETHASONE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF OVERLOAD-INDUCED OSTEOARTHRITIS**

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ABSTRACT

Osteoarthritis (OA) is treated with the intraarticular injection of steroids such as dexamethasone (DEX) to provide short-term pain management. However, DEX treatment suffers from rapid joint clearance. Here, 20×10 μm, shape-defined poly(D,L-lactide-coglycolide) acid (PLGA) microPlates (μPLs) are created and intraarticularly deposited for the sustained release of dexamethasone. Under confined conditions, DEX release is projected to persist for several months, with only ~20% released in the first month. In a highly rigorous murine knee overload injury model (PTOA), a single intraarticular injection of Cy5-μPLs is detected in the cartilage surface, infrapatellar fat pad/synovium, joint capsule, and posterior joint space up to 30 days. One intraarticular injection of DEX-μPL (1 mg kg⁻¹) decreased the expression of IL-1β, TNF-α, IL-6 and MMP-13 by approximately half compared to free DEX at 4 weeks post-treatment. DEX-μPL also reduced load-induced histological changes in the articular cartilage and synovial tissues relative to saline or free DEX. In sum, the μPLs provide sustained drug release along with the capability to precisely control particle geometry and mechanical properties, yielding long-lasting benefits in overload-induced OA. This work motivates further study and development of particles that provide combined pharmacological and mechanical benefits.

KEYWORDS: osteoarthritis, polymeric microparticles, mechanical properties, sustained release, drug depot.

1. INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a prevalent disease that causes chronic pain and disability, especially among the elderly. ¹⁻² OA can also affect younger patients, often due to post-traumatic osteoarthritis (PTOA), a form of OA which can occur after joint, ligament, and bone injury or surgery. ³ PTOA, in opposition to idiopathic age-associated OA, has an identifiable triggering event that makes therapeutics for prevention clinically feasible. OA-associated mechanical wear or traumatic joint injury promote increased expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g. IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α) and matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) in the affected joint. Excessive inflammation reduces the synthesis of extracellular matrix components and increases matrix degradation, driven principally by aggrecanases and MMPs, resulting in lesions in the articular cartilage surface that progress toward full cartilage erosion and complete joint dysfunction. ⁴⁻⁵

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are typically the first line of pharmaceutical treatment but are only marginally effective at pain relief, can cause gastrointestinal complications, and do not slow cartilage deterioration. ⁶⁻⁷ Also, one challenge for NSAID systemic administration is the insufficient accumulation in the joints, which are relatively avascular, making local injection a good alternative for increasing bioavailability and decreasing systemic exposure.

⁷ In current clinical practice, the Osteoarthritis Research Society International (OARSI) and the American College of Rheumatology recommend articular injection of anti-inflammatory corticosteroids for symptomatic knee OA with dexamethasone (DEX) as one of five FDA-approved corticosteroids for this use. ⁷⁻⁹ A limitation of the intraarticular injection of steroids is the lack of local retention as small molecules are cleared through the synovial vasculature and macromolecules drained through the lymphatics, leading to joint half-lives ranging from 1 to 4 hours. ¹⁰

Biomaterial depots offer a reliable approach for improving drug pharmacokinetics, particularly for treating chronic diseases.¹¹⁻¹² To this end, Flexion Therapeutics developed and recently achieved FDA approval for the sustained release of triamcinolone acetonide from poly(D,L-lactide-coglycolide) acid (PLGA) microparticles.¹³ Note that this anti-inflammatory corticosteroid belongs to the same drug class as DEX. Biomaterials for mechanical cushioning in the knee are also applied clinically, with intraarticular injection of hyaluronic acid (HA) being the primary approach used to enhance the mechanical properties of the synovial fluid. HA injections are posited to reduce pain by increasing hydration, lubrication, and resistance to shear in the joint.^{14,15} However, even for larger molecular weight biomacromolecules like HA, the relief is short-lived as the half-life within the joint is approximately 1 day¹⁰, and there is not strong evidence that HA provides palliative benefit over steroid injection.⁷ A promising preclinical approach to repair cartilage structure and mechanical integrity, while also providing a sustained release depot, involves press-fitting drug-loaded, macroscopic gels into cartilage defects.¹⁶ This approach enables long-term (several months) release of DEX directly within the cartilaginous tissue and could be promising for late stage disease, where more invasive surgical intervention is justified.

Our group recently reported an injectable drug depot comprising shape-defined PLGA-based microplates (μ PLs).¹⁷ These micro-constructs exhibit distinct physico-chemical properties, dictated by their size, shape, surface, and mechanical properties which can be simultaneously and independently tailored during the synthesis process. Size and shape control provide desirable formulation homogeneity and reproducibility, while the ability to tune particle surface and mechanical properties can provide application-specific benefits. Here, this technology is applied to produce DEX-loaded polymeric μ PLs (DEX- μ PLs) in order to increase drug exposure within the articular joint. After briefly describing the fabrication process and characterizing the

morphological, mechanical and pharmacological properties of DEX- μ PLs, these particles are tested *in vitro* for their anti-inflammatory potential and *in vivo* for pharmacokinetics and their ability to reduce joint structural changes due to overload injury-associated PTOA.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Synthesis and characterization of dexamethasone-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs).

MicroPlates (μ PLs) were generated using a sacrificial-template fabrication strategy.¹⁷ A silicon master template comprising a two-dimensional (2D) matrix of wells used to define the particles' geometry was first built using a direct laser writing method. Then, a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) template was generated by replicating the original master template. This intermediate PDMS template presents a 2D matrix of pillars with the same geometry as the particles. Finally, a PVA template was produced by replicating the PDMS template (**Figure 1a, b**). This sacrificial template presents a 2D matrix of wells, identical to that of the original master template, which are filled with the polymeric paste (poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) – PLGA) containing the drug payload (**Figure 1c**). Then, the μ PLs were released in an aqueous solution by progressively dissolving the sacrificial PVA template (**Figure 1d**). The microscopy images presented in **Figure 1d** demonstrate the defined and uniform geometry of the μ PLs, presenting a length and width of 20 μ m and a height of 10 μ m.

Particles loaded with curcumin (CURC) (CURC- μ PLs) for visualization purposes (yellow/green) appeared to have a well-defined geometry clearly defined by the wells in the PVA template, which appears red due to the dispersion of a Rhodamine B fluorescent probe (**Figure 1c**). Dissolution of the PVA template in water resulted in the release of the μ PLs, which were then characterized by electron microscopy and a multisizer particle counter (**Figure 1d, e**). A SEM

image of the particles from a 30° tilted view (**Figure 1d**) shows that the size and cuboidal shape of the particles match that of the original template. The analysis of the μ PL number and size distribution by Multisizer (**Figure 1e**) showed a single peak around $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ with a relatively narrow distribution. A topographical analysis, under hydrated conditions, with an optical profilometer (**Figure 1f**) confirmed the values of the particle thickness and the overall geometry. This can be appreciated via the false-coloring 3D reconstruction as well as the cross-section profile, both shown in **Figure 1f**. Similar profilometric data were also generated for lyophilized μ PLs (**Figure S1**) demonstrating a $\sim 10\%$ variation (see **Supporting Information** and **Table. S2**) in volume between the two configurations (fully hydrated particles vs lyophilized particles).

Figure 1: Geometrical characterization of microPlates (μ PLs). **a.** Confocal microscopy and **b.** SEM image of an empty PVA template; **c.** Confocal microscopy image of a PVA template (red) filled with a PLGA/curcumin paste forming CURC- μ PLs (green/yellow); **d.** SEM image of individual μ PLs released from the PVA template. The lateral inset shows a magnified and tilted view of the μ PLs; **e.** Size distribution profile for μ PLs via a Multisizer Coulter Counter analysis; **f.** An optical-profilometer topographic image of a μ PL, where the red-level false coloring correlates with the local particle thickness. The plot on the right represents the cross-sectional profile of the μ PL.

2.2. Pharmacological and mechanical characterization of dexamethasone-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs). The DEX- μ PLs fabrication process was characterized in terms of fabrication yield (number of particles per template), entrapment efficiency (EE), loading efficiency (LE), and amount of DEX per μ PL (**Figure 2a**). As previously reported¹⁷, the fabrication yield, calculated as the ratio between the number of μ PLs collected after PVA dissolution and the theoretical number of wells in a template, was approximately 40%. The amount of DEX loaded per template was $59.2 \pm 9.5 \mu\text{g}$; with LE and EE of $5.0 \pm 0.5\%$ and $12.0 \pm 2.5\%$, respectively. These measured EE and LE values are in line with those in other published literature on PLGA microparticle drug encapsulation.¹⁸⁻¹⁹ The amount of DEX loaded per particle was $159.2 \pm 19.5 \text{ pg}$. Considering the theoretical volume of a single μ PL being $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ nl}$ (i.e. $\text{Volume} = L \times W \times H = 20 \mu\text{m} \times 20 \mu\text{m} \times 10 \mu\text{m} = 4,000 \mu\text{m}^3 = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ nL}$), the DEX volumetric concentration per μ PL was approximately 40 kg m^{-3} . *In vitro* drug release kinetics were measured under two different conditions, namely 4L, which approximates an infinite sink, and 500 μL , which approximates confinement within the synovial cavity after intraarticular injection.²⁰ Briefly, DEX - μ PLs were

kept in 2 different volumes of PBS buffer (1X, pH 7.4), 4L and 500 μ L, at 37 ± 2 °C under magnetic stirring. For the 4L condition, three samples at each time point were collected, centrifuged down and pellets were isolated and dissolved in acetonitrile / H₂O (1:1, v/v) to release the remaining DEX. The resulting solution was analyzed via HPLC to quantify the drug loaded in the μ PLs at each time point. For the 500 μ L condition, three samples at each time point (**Figure 2c**) were collected, centrifuged down and resuspended with 500 μ L of fresh PBS buffer. Then, the supernatants were collected, mixed with acetonitrile, and analyzed via HPLC for drug content. Both release conditions showed profiles consistent with diffusion-controlled release, but with different percentages of released DEX under the two different conditions (**Figure 2b, c**). Specifically, there was a 30% burst release of DEX within the first 8h under the sink condition. Conversely, in the more physiologically relevant condition of 500 μ L, only ~ 4% of DEX was released within the first 8h. In both conditions, the remaining encapsulated DEX was released at a relatively constant rate, yielding approximately 85% release after 10 days under the sink condition and approximately 20% after 30 days in 500 μ L. This sustained drug release from the μ PLs is expected to provide a significant extension in the DEX dwell time within the joint cavity as opposed to its free formulation, which typically has a half-life of 1-4 hours.¹⁰

The initial, faster phase of release is likely associated to DEX molecules residing in the vicinity of the particle surface that would diffuse out more rapidly. On the other hand, the second, slower release phase should be ascribed to the sustained diffusion of the DEX molecules from the particle interior and the progressive degradation of the PLGA matrix of the μ PLs.²¹⁻²² To further analyze the mechanism of release, the profiles of **Figure 2b,c** were fitted with the Weibull function to derive the corresponding coefficients a and b. Specifically, values for b smaller than 0.75 would suggest a release kinetic dominated by Fickian diffusion rather than matrix degradation or

swelling.²³ The values obtained from the best-fit were $a = 0.0014$, $b = 0.34$ ($R^2 = 0.98$) for the sink condition and $a = 0.41$, $b = 0.51$ ($R^2 = 0.99$) for the confined volume release. Thus, μ PLs provide a sustained release of DEX via, predominantly, a diffusion-controlled mechanism through the PLGA matrix within the first few weeks. In order to confirm this, particle degradation under physiologically condition was studied. As shown in **Figure S2**, on Day 0, particles showed the characteristic well-defined squared morphology. On Day 7, images documented a few signs of degradation on some μ PLs. The degradation progressed over time affecting mostly the inner, bottom part of some μ PLs, while the edges of all the particles continued to be well defined for the entire first month of incubation. The gradual transition from a squared geometry to a round microparticle occurs only at the later stage (Day 42). This would lead to conclude that, within the first weeks of incubation, only a modest portion of some μ PLs is biodegraded.

After characterizing the *in vitro* drug release kinetics, a preliminary characterization of the μ PL mechanical properties was performed using nanoindentation and dynamic mechanical analysis. Specifically, a small droplet ($< 1\mu\text{L}$) of a μ PL solution was deposited over a glass slide, dried overnight, and indented with a 200 μm -diameter truncated cone tip. Indentation force-displacement curves were derived as shown in **Figure 2d**, where the average value (line) and the corresponding standard deviation (shadowed area) are presented for three repetitions. From the slope of the force-displacement curves, an apparent modulus was calculated of 3.1 ± 0.9 MPa based on the classical Hertz theory of contact mechanics. In addition to this static characterization, dynamic testing was conducted to characterize the viscoelastic response and potential mechanical dampening behavior of μ PLs. In this case, a small droplet of a μ PL solution was deposited over a glass slide and partially dried in a vacuum desiccator to create a thin particle layer. Then, a sinusoidal force was applied to the μ PL layer, with a frequency of 5 Hz and increasing force

amplitude (0.04, 0.08 and 0.12 N). The phase difference between the input (force) and output (deformation) was recorded over time to extract the phase difference parameter ($\tan \delta$), which is related to the mechanical damping of the system.²⁴ This is shown in **Figure 2e** giving a $\tan \delta$ of ~ 0.3 . This dissipation value is characteristic of materials with high damping and shock absorbing properties²⁵⁻²⁶.

Figure 2: Drug loading, release kinetics, and mechanical characterization of DEX-loaded microPlates (DEX- μPL s). **a.** DEX- μPL fabrication yield and drug loading characterization; **b.** DEX release profile from μPL s under the sink condition (4 L, red line) and Weibull function fitting

(red line; 95% confidence band); **c.** DEX release profile from μ PLs under confined conditions (500 μ L; green line; 95% confident band) and Weibull function fitting; **d.** Force-displacement curve for a flat punch indentation experiment on μ PLs (average curve and standard deviation). In the inset, a schematic of the experimental setup is provided; **e.** Mechanical damping of μ PLs upon cyclic loading (frequency 5 Hz) as a function of the force oscillation amplitude. In the inset, a schematic of the testing routine highlights the phase angle δ - dissipation parameter. Results are presented as the average \pm SD (n=3).

2.3. *In vitro* anti-inflammatory effect of dexamethasone-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs). In order to test potential toxicity effects, the proliferative activity of chondrogenic ATDC5 cells was measured after treatment with DEX, empty- μ PLs, and DEX- μ PLs (**Figure 3a**). Empty- μ PL treatments were defined to contain the same polymeric amounts used for the treatment with DEX- μ PLs. No toxicity effect was observed within a wide range of concentrations of free drug (up to 30 μ M of DEX) and empty microparticles (up to 3 μ PLs per cell). These results are in line with previous tests conducted by the authors on other cells, including primary bone marrow derived monocytes^{17, 27}. Also, the percentage of live and dead cells under different treatments was evaluated using two different techniques: trypan blue count and flow cytometry analysis (FC). As shown in **Figure S3** and the related table, both independent analyses returned ATDC5 viability values well over 90% for all tested experimental groups and at all tested concentrations.

Pro-inflammatory cytokines, produced primarily by synoviocytes and chondrocytes in the joint²⁸, promote the production of proteases that breakdown articular cartilage and collagen fibers.²⁹ Thus, anti-inflammatory properties of the proposed drug delivery system were tested in ATDC5 cells treated with free DEX and DEX- μ PLs, at 1 and 10 μ M DEX concentrations, and then

stimulated with LPS to trigger a rapid and robust pro-inflammatory response³⁰⁻³². DEX- μ PLs and free DEX significantly (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.001$ and *** $p < 0.0001$) reduced the expression of three inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α), as compared to the untreated samples that were just stimulated with LPS (+LPS) (**Figure 3b-d**). A DEX concentration of 1 μ M was sufficient to inhibit the expression of all tested pro-inflammatory genes. The higher DEX concentration (10 μ M) did not appear to significantly enhance the anti-inflammatory activity as compared to the lower dose. These data suggest that DEX- μ PLs reduce the production of inflammatory cytokines by ATDC5 cells in response to potent pro-inflammatory stimuli. Similar results were previously reported by the authors on different cell types, including bone marrow derived monocytes^{17, 27}, confirming the anti-inflammatory properties of DEX- μ PLs across multiple cell types relevant to PTOA. Also, as documented in the **Figure S4**, the empty- μ PLs did not induce any increase in pro-inflammatory cytokine expression at both tested particle concentrations demonstrating that empty- μ PLs lack any pro- or anti-inflammatory activity

Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) was performed in order to observe the interaction between the fluorescently labeled μ PLs and ATDC5 cells. **Figure 3e, f** and **Figure S5-6** confirm the absence of μ PL internalization by ATDC5 cells and macrophages, suggesting that the particles would be retained extracellularly³³⁻³⁵, and therefore release DEX into the articular cartilage and intraarticular space to affect cells throughout the joint. Note that these particles are not expected to be phagocytosed but, instead, to biodegrade over time, releasing lactic and glycolic acid byproducts that enter the Krebs` cycle to be eliminated as CO₂ and water.³⁶

Figure 3: *In vitro* cytocompatibility and anti-inflammatory effect of DEX-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs). **a.** ATDC5 cell viability upon incubation with free DEX, empty- μ PLs, and DEX- μ PLs. Statistical analysis via one-way ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 5), is provided in the **Table. S3**;

b. – d. Expression levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α for LPS stimulated ATDC5 cells. (**-LPS**: no LPS and no μ PLs; **+LPS**: LPS stimulation and no μ PLs; **DEX**: LPS stimulation and free DEX at 1 and 10 μ M; **DEX- μ PLs**: LPS treatment and DEX- μ PLs at 1 and 10 μ M). Results are presented as average \pm SD ($n \geq 4$). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.001$ and *** $p < 0.0001$ were considered statistically significant as compared to the control (+LPS); ## $p < 0.001$ and ### $p < 0.0001$ were considered statistically significant as compared to 1 μ M DEX and °° $p < 0.001$ and °°° $p < 0.0001$ were considered statistically significant as compared to 10 μ M DEX. Lack of statistically significant difference between groups is indicated on the graphs as NS. Multiple comparisons were performed using, as post hoc test, the Tukey's significant difference (HSD) test;

e. a 30° tilted view of a SEM image of ATDC5 cells incubated with μ PLs. In the lateral inset, a magnified image shows cells interacting with μ PLs; **f.** false-color SEM image of a μ PL (red) deposited and not internalized over a layer of ATDC5 cells (green).

2.4. *In vivo* Pharmacokinetic, Biodistribution, and Confocal Microscopy

Characterization of Cy5- μ PLs. To assess the intraarticular retention time, the near infrared dye Cy5 was directly conjugated to the polymeric matrix of μ PLs. Specifically, the carboxylic groups on the PLGA chain of μ PLs were activated, via an EDC/NHS reaction, and then covalently coupled to the free amine group of the Cy5 molecule modified with a 1,8-Diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane. The stability of the resulting Cy5- μ PLs was evaluated upon particle incubation in PBS, at 37 ± 2 °C, up to 1 month (same duration of the *in vivo* experiment). As reported in **Figure S7**, after 24 h in PBS, $83.9 \pm 1.6\%$ of Cy5 molecules remained covalently bound to the μ PL PLGA matrix.

A time-course of intravital imaging, *ex-vivo* imaging, organ biodistribution, and confocal microscopy analyses was performed following a single intraarticular injection of Cy5- μ PLs into

a cohort of mice with mechanically-induced post-traumatic osteoarthritis (PTOA). The Cy5 fluorescence signal in the joint, associated with μ PLs, was captured over 20 days via intravital imaging (**Figure 4a, top row**) and for the entire time course of 30 days via the more sensitive *ex-vivo* analysis with the skin removed from the limb (**Figure 4a, bottom row**). This was translated into an intravital fraction of particle retention as a function of time, as plotted in **Figure 4b**. The initial, transient increase in fluorescence within the joints in the first day after injection (**Figure 4b**) is a result of loss of fluorophore self-quenching, which occurs due to high density fluorophore conjugation into the particles. Confocal microscopy performed 1 day after injection showed the Cy5- μ PLs dispersed across the entire knee joint (**Figure 4c**), reaching the femoral-tibial cartilage interface, the infrapatellar fat pad and synovium, and the joint capsule. Magnified images at 1 day after injection showed deposition of Cy5- μ PLs on top of the articular cartilage surface, near the cartilage/synovium interface and the joint capsule (**Figure 4d**). Magnified images of Cy5- μ PLs within the joint space at different time points document a heterogenous loss of Cy5 fluorescence over time, which could be correlated with surface particle erosion and distortion (**Figure 4e, Figure S8-S9**). At the later timepoints, Cy5- μ PLs were seen mostly in the surrounding synovial, joint capsule, and soft-tissue structures rather than the cartilage interface (**Figure 4e, Figure S8-S9**). This may result from a combination of factors including greater degradation at the cartilage interface, the loading process pushing synovial fluid (and consequently microplates) to the surrounding soft tissue structures, and histological sampling. Finally, biodistribution analyses showed the Cy5 fluorescence signal to be mostly localized within the knee joints (**Figure S10**).

Figure 4: *In vivo* pharmacokinetic study of Cy5-conjugated microPlates (Cy5 - μ PLs) in a PTOA mouse model. **a. Representative pharmacokinetic timecourse intravital images (skin on) and *ex-vivo* knee images (skin off) of Cy5- μ PLs injected intraarticularly into PTOA mouse knee joints (D-#, where # represents days after intraarticular injection). **b.** Intravital fraction of retention of Cy5- μ PLs plotted as mean + SEM. Note = The initial uptake in fluorescence within the joints**

in the first couple of hours after injection is a result of loss of fluorophore self-quenching, which occurs due to high density fluorophore conjugation onto the particles. **c.** Anatomically labelled sagittal section of a mouse knee joint 1 day after intraarticular injection showing the Cy5- μ PLs dispersed across the joint interacting and/or in close proximity to many different tissue types such as the cartilage, the infrapatellar fat pad and synovium, and the joint capsule. **d.** Confocal microscopy imaging performed 1 day after intraarticular injection showing Cy5- μ PLs located on top of the cartilage surface, near the cartilage/synovium interface, and the joint capsule. In all images, the scale bar = 100 μ m. **e.** Confocal microscopy imaging of Cy5- μ PLs within the mouse knee joint taken at different time points after intraarticular injection. TD = Transmission Detector. NT = No Treatment. For intravital imaging analysis, n = 4-24 limbs depending on the time point. I.e., earlier time points had more animals included, and the sample size at the later timepoints was lower because some animals were taken down at earlier timepoints for ex-vivo and confocal microscopy analysis. For ex-vivo imaging analysis and confocal microscopy analysis, n = 2-4 limbs per time point.

2.5. Therapeutic assessment of DEX- μ PLs in an overload-induced osteoarthritis mouse model. Next, a 4-week *in vivo* study was completed in a PTOA mouse model where the animals' knees were placed in flexion and loaded in compression using a custom fitting, as depicted in **Figure 5a**. A single intraarticular dose of DEX (1 mg kg⁻¹) was administered into each knee, as free DEX or DEX- μ PLs, starting concurrently with mechanical loading. An identical quantity of μ PLs without DEX was administered as a vehicle control. The DEX dose (animal weight adjusted) was chosen based on a dose that previously produced robust anti-inflammatory effects in rabbits³⁷ and rats.³⁸ Following 4 weeks of mechanical loading, qPCR was employed to assess expression

of genes associated with PTOA progression on the combined tibial and femoral cartilage surfaces and synovial tissue (**Figure 5b**). Expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α , in addition to matrix metalloproteinase-13 (MMP-13) was assessed. Note that MMP-13 is a primary driver of degradation of the key cartilage structural protein type II collagen.³⁹ The data presented in **Figure 5c**, supported by the computed p-values listed in the **Table. S4**, show that DEX- μ PLs (red square) significantly reduced all genes assayed compared to untreated knees (black cross) (p values: IL-1 β = 0.0013, TNF- α = 0.0222, IL-6 = 0.0083, MMP-13 = 0.0053) and free DEX (blue circle) (p values: IL-1 β = 0.0024, TNF- α = 0.0244, IL-6 = 0.0376, MMP-13 = 0.0107). Interestingly, empty- μ PLs (green triangle) did significantly reduce the expression of MMP-13 as compared to untreated knees (p value: 0.0086) and free DEX (p value: 0.0268). The marked reduction of expression for all inflammatory genes measured from a single dose of DEX- μ PLs at the end of a rigorous 4-week (5 times per week) loading protocol implies a prolonged pharmacological effect of DEX- μ PLs due to extended DEX availability within the intraarticular space. On the other hand, the therapeutic effect of free DEX on cartilage structure and synovial health has been shown at comparable doses in rabbits to dissipate within 3 weeks of injection without formulation, further validating the observed extension of benefit from DEX- μ PLs over free DEX.⁴⁰

Figure 5: Pro-inflammatory gene expression in a PTOA model mouse. **a.** Schematic of the loading fixture used in the mechanical loading of mouse knee joints to induce PTOA; **b.** mechanical loading regimen; **c.** *in vivo* expression of IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-6, and MMP-13 measured by TaqMan qPCR (for each treatment groups n=6, while for the healthy group n=4). Statistical analysis via one-way ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 8), corrected for multiple comparisons by controlling the False Discovery Rate with a two-stage, step-up Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli method: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, while no significant differences are indicated on the graphs as NS. Full list of p-values is provided in the **Table. S4**.

Histology was also performed to assess the progression of PTOA in terms of structural deterioration of the articular cartilage and synovial response. Sections of each joint were stained with Safranin O and Fast Green to assess damage to the articular cartilage surface. Safranin O is a cationic dye that binds to proteoglycans, which are structural molecules depleted in the context of OA. This stain is used for grading the severity of OA by the Osteoarthritis Research Society International (OARSI) scoring method.⁴¹⁻⁴² A treatment-blinded histopathologist assessed Safranin O slides using the OARSI scale and found that DEX- μ PLs (red bar) and empty- μ PLs (green bar) significantly reduced the OARSI severity score compared to untreated joints (black bar) (p values: 0.037 and 0.01, respectively) (**Figure 6a**). Free DEX (blue bar) was not found to provide a significant difference in OARSI score relative to untreated PTOA control knees.

Because OA is a total joint disease that involves remodeling of and crosstalk with the synovium, meniscus, and underlying subchondral bone^{29, 43}, hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was also used to appraise overall joint health and more specifically inflammation, fibrosis, thickening, and mineralization in the surrounding soft tissues (synovium and meniscus). Treatment-blinded histopathological scoring was also completed with the Degenerative Joint Disease (DJD) Score, a joint scoring approach meant to complement the OARSI score by appraising joint health beyond cartilage integrity with regards to meniscal metaplasia / fragmentation, osteophyte formation, capsule fibrosis, and synovitis/synovial hyperplasia (**Table S1**). DJD scoring revealed that DEX- μ PLs (red bar) and empty- μ PLs (green bar) significantly improved overall joint health over the untreated knees (black bar) (p value: 0.0027 and 0.0437, respectively) (**Figure 6b**). Also, DEX- μ PLs (red bar) did better than free DEX (blue bar) (p-value: 0.0012) in terms of DJD scoring (**Figure 6b**). The load-induced arthritis model in these studies is very aggressive and triggers a very intense onset of PTOA-associated changes in the knee joint,

including synovial hyperplasia, osteophyte formation, chondrophyte formation, and ectopic mineralization in the synovium and meniscus. Joints treated with empty μ PLs and DEX- μ PLs showed milder and less mature chondrophyte formation, cellular infiltration, and synovial membrane thickening relative to the saline treated animals. The saline treated PTOA mice in particular showed much more advanced chondrophytes and osteophytes, showing signs of ectopic mineralization of the meniscus and synovium. These histological data confirm the significant therapeutic effect of DEX- μ PLs as manifested by the reduction for the OARSI score and the DJD score as compared to the untreated and free-DEX treated knees.

up Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli method; all images are matched in scale. **b.** H&E staining of PTOA joints showing a representative slide for each treatment group (Histology: # - mineralization, * - cellular infiltration and synovial membrane thickening); inserts show higher magnification images of synovial tissue (top) and Degenerative Joint Disease scoring of the joint histology by a treatment-blinded pathologist (bottom, * $p < 0.05$, while no significant differences are indicated on the graphs as NS); Statistical significance via one-way ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 8), corrected for multiple comparisons by controlling the False Discovery Rate with a two-stage, step-up Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli method, statistically; all images are matched in scale. In the lower magnification images, scale bar = 1 mm, while higher magnification images scale bar = 100 μm (for each treatment groups $n=6$, while for the healthy group $n= 4$).

3. DISCUSSION

Herein, we report that DEX-loaded μPLs with specific geometrical and mechanical properties could provide significant therapeutic benefits to PTOA joints. It is well-documented that intraarticularly injected micron-sized particles, like the $20 \times 20 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ μPLs , would not be drained away from the joint via the synovial capillaries and lymphatics but would rather distribute within the synovial fluid and at the interface with the synovial lining and the articular cartilage.¹⁴
⁴⁴⁻⁴⁵ This was evident in the *in vivo* pharmacokinetic study where intravital, *ex-vivo* and confocal microscopy imaging detected Cy5- μPLs in the joint, particularly on top of the cartilage surfaces, near the infrapatellar fat pad/synovium and the joint capsule for up to 30 days. These are all sites of pathologic inflammation in arthropathies, including osteoarthritis. Furthermore, the Cy5 signal was detected mostly in the knee joint with low levels seen in metabolic/clearance organs. This is consistent with the original objective as DEX- μPLs were designed to reside within the joint cavity

and sustainably release DEX as a means to mitigate pro-inflammatory signals within the joint. Given the limited volume of the human synovial cavity (~ 3 mL) and the release rates documented in **Figure 2c** under confined volume conditions, DEX could be sustainably released for several weeks to months from DEX- μ PLs. Based on multiple reports, a strong anti-inflammatory activity results in pronounced differences in outcomes in the early stages of the disease, when inflammatory cytokines are mostly produced by macrophages and fibroblastic synoviocytes residing in the synovium.^{2, 46-47} This could explain the significant reduction in the production of cytokines observed in the joints of mice treated with the DEX- μ PLs as compared to free DEX, which has a half-life in the joint of only a few hours.¹⁰ Other publications corroborate the lack of protective effect of free DEX after 3 – 4 weeks, and highlight the value of a platform that can continuously release DEX for a sustained period of time.^{40,48} Importantly, no statistically significant difference was observed between the untreated and free-DEX treated knees in cytokine production and MMP-13 expression (see **Table. S4.**) or for the two histological scoring systems applied (see OARSI score in **Figure 6a** and DJD score in **Figure 6b**).

A notable advantage of DEX- μ PLs over other microparticle drug delivery systems is the opportunity to precisely tailor the μ PL size, geometry, surface and mechanical properties during the top-down fabrication process. The size of μ PLs can range from a few to several tens of micrometers; the fabrication templates can be altered to yield particles with a range of geometries; while the deformability can vary from a few kPa to tens of MPa depending on the amounts of PLGA used.^{17, 27} Moreover, the surface physico-chemical properties of μ PLs can be modulated to facilitate their biochemical interaction with cartilage and HA in the synovial fluid, both of which are anionic. From the initial therapeutic findings, future work is merited to more rigorously study

the interplay between the pharmacological efficacy of the DEX-loaded μ PLs and the potential of mechanically tuning the μ PLs to affect the rheological properties of the synovial fluid.

Finally, it is important to recall that studies in mice always have limitations when compared to an authentic human traumatic joint injury as the size scale and tissue content and architecture differ between species. However, it is important to highlight that the murine model utilized in the present study to create accelerated PTOA has the advantages of being applied to pathophysiologically-relevant aged (6-month old) mice and of being based on rigorous cyclic mechanical loading⁴⁹ rather than commonly used surgical or chemical OA induction procedures that lack clinical relevance or introduce confounding factors into therapeutic studies.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, size-, shape-, and mechanically defined, monodispersed PLGA microplates (μ PLs) were applied for the intraarticular delivery of dexamethasone. A top-down approach was used for μ PL fabrication, obtaining consistently shaped particles with a dimension of 20 μ m per side and a height of 10 μ m. The anti-inflammatory molecule DEX was efficiently loaded into μ PLs, and the resultant formulation achieved continuous release over a period of 10 days at infinite sink conditions and at least 1 month in biologically relevant, confined volumes. The DEX- μ PLs reduced inflammatory gene expression both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. In a highly rigorous model of post-traumatic overload-induced osteoarthritis, a single intra-articular injection of Cy5- μ PLs was detected in the joint space for up to 30 days. In the same animal model, a single intraarticular injection of DEX- μ PLs holistically protected both the articular cartilage and the broader joint structure through 4 weeks of rigorous mechanical overloading of the joints. In sum, this work

provides a proof of concept for the utility of shaped-defined and deformable μ PLs in the protection against PTOA-associated joint deterioration.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

The Supporting Information provided are: Safranin O scoring of tibial plateau cartilage degeneration and H&E scoring of overall stifle degenerative joint disease (**Table. S1.**); Microplate volumes prior and after lyophilization via optical profilometric analysis. (**Table. S2.**); List of p value for experimental groups of **Figure 3a** (**Table S3.**); List of p-values for all the experimental groups of **Figure 5.** (**Table. S4.**); A profilometric analysis of hydrated and lyophilized μ PLs. (**Figure.S1**); Particles degradation (**Figure S2.**); Determination of live/dead cells after dexamethasone-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs) (**Figure S3.**); *In vitro* effect of empty microPlates (μ PLs) (**Figure.S.4**); ATDC5 cells interaction with microPlates (**Figure.S5.**); RAW 264.7 macrophags interacting with microPlates (**Figure.S6.**); Cy5- μ PL stability (**Figure.S7.**); 20x Images of Cy5- μ PLs within a mouse model of PTOA at multiple time points (**Figure.S8.**); Magnified images of Cy5- μ PLs within a mouse model of PTOA at multiple time points (**Figure.S9.**); Cy5- μ PLs *ex-vivo* organ biodistribution in a mouse model of PTOA at multiple time points (**Figure.S10.**).

5. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

5.1. Materials. Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) (Sylgard 184) and elastomer were obtained from Dow Corning (Midland, Michigan, USA). Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, Mw 31,000–50,000), poly(D,L-lactide-coglycolide) acid (PLGA, lactide:glycolide 50:50, Mw 38,000–54,000), dexamethasone acetate (DEX), 1-ethyl-3-(3-(dimethylamino)propyl)-carbodiimide (EDC), N-

hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), acetonitrile, ATDC-5 cell line, MTT assay, bacterial lipopolysaccharides (LPS), paraformaldehyde (PFA), Propidium Iodide (PI) and trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Saint Louis, Missouri, USA). High-glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's minimal essential medium (DMEM) / F-12 GlutaMAX, high-glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's minimal essential medium (DMEM) penicillin, streptomycin and heat inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS) were purchased from Gibco (Invitrogen Corporation, Giuliano Milanese, Milan, Italy). RAW 264.7 cell line was obtained from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, LGC Standards, Teddington, UK). Cyanine5 NHS ester was purchased from Luminoprobe (Hunt Valley, MD, US). 1,8-Diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane and Curcumin (CURC) were purchased from Alfa Aesar (Haverhill, Massachusetts, USA). C57BL/6 mice were purchased from Jackson Laboratory (Bar Harbor, Maine, USA). Mouse study TaqMan primers (IL- 6: Mm01210732_g1, IL- 1 β : Mm00434228_m1, TNF- α : Mm00443258_m1, MMP13: Mm00439491_m1) and reagents (as directed by standard protocols) were all purchased from Thermo fisher Scientific (Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). All the reagents and other solvents were used as received.

5.2. MicroPlates (μ PLs) fabrication process. μ PLs were synthesized using a top down approach, as previously reported.^{17, 27} Briefly, the silicon master template was developed using direct laser writing (DLW), which allows transfer of a specific pattern on the silicon. In this case, the pattern is made out of square wells with a length ($\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$) and a height ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) characteristic size and shape of the microPlates. The silicon pattern was replicated into PDMS and then, into PVA templates, which showed the same arrays as the original silicon master template. The mixture of PLGA and drug (none in empty controls) were filled into the holes of PVA sacrificial templates.

Particles were obtained after the purification from PVA solution. Each batch of particles for all *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments was synthesized using 15 mg of PLGA, and when appropriate, DEX was dispersed in the polymeric mixture at 3.2 weight percentage (500 µg). For all *in vitro* studies, dose of DEX was adjusted based on total particle mass added, and amount of DEX relative PLGA mass was not adjusted as a variable in these studies. 30 µL of 1,8-Diamino-3,6-dioxaoctane was dissolved in dichloromethane (DCM, 3mL) and methanol (MeOH, 1.5mL). Cyanine-5 NHS ester (0.25 eq) was dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF, 200 mL) and added to the previous solution. A catalytic amount of triethylamine (TEA) was add to the reaction which was left to stir for 16 h. The intended product was precipitated with cold diethyl ether. The product was washed 3 times with cold diethyl ether getting a final product with a yield of 85%⁵⁰.

For assessing *in vivo* µPLs pharmacokinetic and biodistribution, Cy5 was covalently conjugated to the surface of particles. This was required to ensure the stable attachment of the fluorophore to the particle. Briefly, purified µPLs were incubated with EDC/NHS at a molar ratio of 3:1 for 5h under rotation at room temperature. After removing unlinked activators (5 min centrifuge at 1717g), activated µPLs (around 400,000 particles) were incubated overnight with Cy5 (50 µg). Free, unlinked Cy5 was removed with washing steps (5 min centrifuge at 1717g).

5.3. µPLs size, size distribution, and shape. µPLs size and shape were assessed via scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Elios Nanolab 650, FEI). Briefly, a drop of sample was placed on a silicon template and sputtered with 10 nm of gold. Samples were analyzed with the instrument operating at an acceleration voltage of 5–15 keV. µPLs concentration and size distribution were also measured through a Multisizer 4 COULTER particle counter (Beckman Coulter, USA). Morphology was examined by optical profilometry on a ZETA-20 optical profilometer (ZETA

Instruments, San Jose, CA) equipped with a 100X objective, with a corresponding vertical resolution of 10 nm.

5.4. μ PLs drug loading and release characterization. DEX loading efficiency (LE) and encapsulation efficiency (EE) of DEX- μ PLs were evaluated as previously reported.^{17, 27} Briefly, before the high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis, samples were lyophilized and dissolved in acetonitrile/H₂O (1:1, v/v). The HPLC (Agilent 1260 Infinity, Germany) was equipped with a 100 μ L sample loop injector and a C18 column (4.6 \times 250 mm, 5 μ m particle size, Agilent, USA) for chromatographic separation. An isocratic condition (H₂O + 0.1% (v/v) TFA/AcN + 0.1% (v/v) TFA, 50:50 v/v, 0.3 mL/min) was applied for DEX elution.

$$LE (\%) = \frac{\text{amount of DEX in the particles}}{\text{total mass of particles}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

$$EE (\%) = \frac{\text{amount of DEX in the particles}}{\text{initial amount of DEX}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

The kinetics of DEX release from μ PLs was measured. To mimic an infinite sink condition, 200 μ L of DEX- μ PLs, corresponding to 10 μ M DEX, were put into Slide-A-Lyzer MINI dialysis micro tubes with a molecular cutoff of 10 kDa (Thermo Scientific) and then dialyzed against 4 L of PBS buffer (pH 7.4, 1X, 37 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C). For each time point, three samples were collected and centrifuged (1717g for 5 min). Pellets were then dissolved in acetonitrile / H₂O (1:1, v/v) and analyzed by HPLC. To evaluate the DEX release profile in a confined microenvironment, DEX- μ PLs, corresponding to 10 μ M DEX, were placed in three eppendorf tubes in 500 μ L PBS buffer (pH 7.4, 1X, 37 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C) under continuous rotation. For each time point, samples were collected and centrifuged (1717g for 5 min). 100 μ L of supernatant was added to 100 μ L of acetonitrile, and the resultant samples were analyzed by HPLC. Pellets were then resuspended with 500 μ L of fresh

PBS buffer (pH 7.4, 1X). The experimental data were fitted to the two-phase Weibull equation model²³:

$$(M_t)/(M_\infty) = 1 - \exp(-a * t^b) \quad (\text{Equation 3}),$$

where M_t and M_∞ are the amounts of drug released at time t and equilibrium (infinite time), respectively. The variable a is a constant based on the system, and b is a constant based on the release kinetics. Values of $b < 0.75$ indicate that Fickian diffusion, not matrix degradation, is the dominant release mechanism.²³

5.5. μ PLs degradation study

μ PLs matrix biodegradation was evaluated by SEM, as previously reported. Empty μ PLs were incubated in PBS (pH= 7.4, 1X) under rotation at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. At predetermined time points, an aliquot of the sample was collected and analyzed at SEM to investigate structural and morphological changes.

5.6. Cy5- μ PLs stability and release profile.

To assess Cy5- μ PLs stability over time, the release profile of Cy5 from μ PLs was investigated. Cy5- μ PLs were placed in three eppendorf tubes in 500 μL of PBS buffer (pH 7.4, 1X, $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) under continuous rotation. For each time point, samples were collected and centrifuged (1717g for 5 min). Supernatants were dried and then resuspended in 200 μL of acetonitrile, and the resultant samples were analyzed using a microplate spectrophotometer with λ_{ex} 630 nm and λ_{emi} 660nm (Tecan, Männedorf, Swiss). Pellets were then resuspended with 500 μL of fresh PBS buffer (pH 7.4, 1X).

5.7. Mechanical characterization of μ PLs. The apparent elastic modulus of μ PLs was measured by flat punch micro-indentation tests. Small droplets ($< 1\mu\text{L}$) of a μ PL suspension were deposited over a glass slide, covering an area of $\sim 5\text{ mm}^2$ with multiple particles and dried overnight. Micro-indentation was performed on an UNHT Nanoindentation platform (Anton Paar) equipped with a $200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ -diameter truncated cone tip. Load was applied at a rate of 20 mN/min until the maximum load of 3 mN . From the slope of the force-displacement curves, the modulus was calculated through the classical Hertzian equation $F = 2REh$ where F is the applied force, h the tip displacement, R the tip radius, E the apparent elastic modulus. Three repetitions were conducted on different droplets.

The energy dissipation capability was characterized by Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) on a Q800 system (TA Instruments). Highly concentrated μ PL solutions were deposited on a glass slide and partially dried in a vacuum desiccator for 10 min to create a thin layer of μ PLs. Then the glass slide was transferred onto the bottom plate of a compressive clamp. A pre-load was applied gently, squeezing out excess water. A sinusoidal force was applied to the layer of μ PLs with the frequency of 5 Hz and increasing amplitude ($0.04, 0.08$ and 0.12 N). The phase difference between the input (force) and output (deformation) was recorded as a function of the oscillation amplitude. The tangent of the phase difference angle, noted as $\tan \delta$, represents the ratio between dissipative and conservative energy during one oscillation and, as such, provides a measure of the damping capability of the material. Tests were conducted at 37°C .

5.8. Toxicity of DEX - μ PLs. ATDC5 cells were cultured at 37°C in 5% CO_2 , in DMEM / F-12, GlutaMAX medium supplemented with 10% FBS, 1% penicillin/streptomycin. For the cell viability assay, cells at 80% confluence were seeded into 96-well plates at 10×10^3 cells per well.

After 24 h of incubation, cells were treated using different concentrations of free DEX, DEX - μ PLs (namely, 0.01, 0.5, 1, 10, and 30 μ M of DEX in all cases), or an equivalent number of empty μ PLs matching the different DEX- μ PLs concentrations. The cytotoxicity was measured with the MTT assay (cell viability test). At the end of the designated incubation times, 5 mg/mL of MTT solution in PBS buffer was added to each well, and the cells were incubated for 4 h at 37 °C. The solubilized formazan product was quantified using a microplate spectrophotometer at 570 nm, using 650 nm as the reference wavelength (Tecan, Männedorf, Swiss). The percentage of cell viability was assessed according to the following equation:

$$\text{Cell Viability (\%)} = \frac{Abs_t}{Abs_c} \times 100 \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

where Abs_t and Abs_c were the absorbance of treated and control (untreated) cells, respectively.

5.9. Evaluation of the percentage of live/dead cells after treatment with of DEX - μ PLs. 2×10^5 cells were seeded into each well of a 12-well plate and after 24h cells were treated with free DEX, DEX- μ PLs (namely, 0.01, 0.5, 1, 10, and 30 μ M of DEX) or an equivalent number of empty- μ PLs, for an additional 24h. Then, the medium was removed from each well and collected. Cells were trypsinized, washed, and counted in presence of trypan blue, which is excluded by live cells while entering dead cells. count, cells were counted using Countess II Automated Cell Counter (Thermofisher) after the addition of Trypan blue dye to discriminate live versus death cells. For the flow cytometry analysis, the collected cells were centrifuged and resuspended in PBS containing propidium iodide (PI), according to the vendor's instruction. After 15 min of incubation, each sample was analyzed using FACS ARIA (Becton Dickinson, USA). A cell population was selected setting a scatter gate that would exclude the negligible amounts of debris and aggregates.

5.10. Inflammatory gene expression effects of DEX - μ PLs *in vitro*. To study the the anti-inflammatory activity of DEX - μ PLs in stimulated ATDC5, the expression levels of the three proinflammatory cytokines tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α , interleukin (IL)-1 β , and IL-6, were evaluated. Cells were seeded into 6-well plates at 3×10^5 cells per well for 24 h. After 5 h of pre-incubation with free DEX, DEX- μ PLs at different concentrations (1 and 10 μ M) or an equivalent number of empty μ PLs matching the two DEX- μ PL concentrations, cells were stimulated for 4 h with bacterial LPS (100 ng/mL). Then, RNA was extracted using a RNeasy Plus Mini Kit (Qiagen) and quantified by NanoDrop2000 (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). Real-time RT-PCR was used to measure mRNA levels of inflammatory cytokines. For each condition, samples were run in triplicate. RT-PCR reactions were carried out using a Power SYBR Green RNA-to-CT 1-Step Kit (Applied Biosystems) and using GAPDH expression as a housekeeping gene. Reactions were performed in a final volume of 20 μ L. Oligonucleotide primer pairs were as follows: for GAPDH, 5'- GAACATCATCCCTGCATCCA-3' a n d 5 '- CCAGTGAGCTTCCCGTTCA-3'; for TNF- α , 5'-GGTGCCTATGTCTCAGCCTCTT- 3' and 5'-GCCATAGAACTGATGAGAGGGAG-3'; for IL- 1 β , 5'-TGGACCTTCCAGGATGAGGACA-3' and 5'- GTTCATCTCGGAGCCTGTAGTG-3'; for IL- 6, 5'-TACCACTTCACAAGTCGGAGGC-3' and 5'-CTGCAAGTGCATCATCGTTGTTC-3'.

5.11. Cell/ μ PL interaction as analyzed by confocal microscopy. To evaluate μ PL cellular interactions, ATDC5 cells were seeded into a 8-chambered cover glass system (Lab Teck II, Thermo Scientific, USA) at 20×10^3 cells per well and incubated for 24 h. The cells were then incubated overnight with CURC- μ PLs (curcumin loading used for fluorescence visualization

purposes). The cells were fixed using 4% PFA, stained red using Alexa Fluor™ 488 Phalloidin (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), and nuclear stained using DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) following vendor instructions. Samples were analyzed using confocal microscopy (Nikon A1, Dexter, MI).

5.12. Cell/ μ PL interaction as analyzed by SEM analysis. To evaluate μ PL cellular interactions within ATDC5 cell line and phagocytic cell lines (RAW 264.7 macrophages), 20×10^4 cells were seeded onto glass coverslips for 24 h. The cells were then incubated overnight with μ PLs at a ratio of 1:4 (μ PL:cells). Samples were fixed for 2 h in 2% glutaraldehyde in 0.1 M cacodylate buffer. After fixation, the samples were washed thrice with the same buffer and post fixed for 1 h in 1% osmium tetroxide in distilled water. After several washes with distilled water, the samples were subsequently dehydrated in a graded ethanol series, 1:1 ethanol:hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS), and 100% HMDS, followed by drying overnight in air. Dried samples were then mounted on stubs using silver conductive paint and coated with gold. SEM images were collected with scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Elios Nanolab 650, FEI) operating at an accelerating voltage between 5 and 15 KeV.

5.13. *In vivo* pharmacokinetic and biodistribution study. An *in vivo* pharmacokinetic study was performed following the same loading and injection regimen as the mechanical-loading model described below (5.13). Cy5 conjugated microplates (Cy5- μ PLs) were injected intraarticularly (as described in 5.13) and mice were imaged intravitaly for Cy5 fluorescence over time using an IVIS Lumina III intravital imaging system (Caliper Life Sciences, Hopkinton, MA). For IVIS image analysis, regions of interest (ROIs) were drawn around both the right and the left knees. For each

mouse knee, a pre-injection reading (blank) was taken followed by a time 0 (T_0) reading directly after intraarticular injection. The blank reading was used for background correction of all images of the same mouse knee at all time points, and dividing the radiance reading (at a specific timepoint) by the T_0 radiance reading was used to calculate 'fraction of retention' at all later timepoints. Animals were euthanized at days 1, 3, 5, 7, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 post-injection along with control no treatment animals (NT). At takedown, the skin was removed from the legs, and the knees were endpoint imaged '*ex-vivo*' for Cy5 fluorescence which provides better sensitivity than intravital imaging. Organs were also harvested for Cy5 fluorescence biodistribution. After *ex-vivo* imaging, excess muscle was removed, and legs were then snap frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until cryosectioning. For intravital imaging analysis, $n = 4-24$ limbs depending on the time point i.e. earlier time points had more animals included as animals were taken down over time for *ex-vivo* and confocal microscopy analysis. For *ex-vivo* imaging analysis and confocal microscopy analysis, $n = 2-4$ limbs per time point.

5.14. Cryosection and confocal microscopy. Legs (stored at -80°C) were embedded into OCT freezing compound, cooled, and serial sectioned in sagittal orientation until an adequate depth of the joint was reached. Cryosections at various depths along the joint were then sectioned at $20\mu\text{m}$ thick, captured utilizing a commercially available polyvinylidene chloride film coated with synthetic rubber cement (<http://section-lab.jp/>), and placed on a slide. Slides were then fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 5 minutes, cover slipped with an aqua mount, and imaged on a Nikon Eclipse Ti inverted confocal microscope. Imaging settings were kept constant for imaging of all Cy5- μPLs -containing joint samples at each time point ($n = 2-4$ limbs per time point). TD = transmission detector.

5.15. *In vivo* mechanical loading OA model. Using a protocol approved by the Vanderbilt Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee, the PTOA model of noninvasive repetitive joint loading was adapted from previous studies⁵¹⁻⁵² to induce PTOA in the knee joints of mice using cyclical mechanical stress. The 28 C57BL/6 mice were aged to 6 months and subjected to a rigorous cyclic mechanical loading (on mice anesthetized with 3% isoflurane) at 9 N per load, 500 cycles per session, cycle lasting 2.5 seconds, 5 loading sessions per week, for 4 weeks using a TA Electroforce 3100 (TA instruments, New Castle, Delaware, USA).⁴⁹ Cyclic loading is performed utilizing form-fitting inserts, one that covers and stabilizes the kneecap and another that holds the ankle with both in a flexed position of 135 degrees. Specifically, the mold for the kneecap is a half-sphere cavity measuring 5 mm in diameter, and the mold for the ankle is a cavity shaped as an equilateral triangular measuring 5 mm in diameter on each side. All loading is performed under anesthesia. Treatment groups each had 6 mice per group while the unloaded, non-OA controls were 4 per group. Following synthesis, DEX-loaded and empty μ PLs were dried and stored at +4 °C until the time of administration. μ PLs were resuspended in PBS by 30 seconds of sonication immediately before intraarticular injection in 20 μ L total volume. Intra-articular injections were administered medial to the patella and validated by repeated dye injections to ensure articular delivery was successful. Dosing and rationale are described in the therapeutic assessment section. All treatment groups were administered a single time at the initiation of the mechanical loading.

5.16. Inflammatory gene expression analysis from *in vivo* PTOA study. Gene expression was analyzed from homogenized cartilage and synovial tissues from one knee per animal with the primers and reagents listed in the materials section. Under a surgical microscope, the cartilage of

the tibial and femoral surfaces were excised by a scalpel, and combined with synovial tissue at about a 1:1 cartilage/tissue mass ratio. Tissue homogenization was performed with 5mm TissueLyser steel beads (Qiagen) in two mL tubes for 5 minutes at 30 Hz, and RNA was collected using the RNeasy mini-prep kit (Qiagen). The iScript cDNA RT kit (Bio Rad) was used for cDNA production. TaqMan qPCR primers and reagents were used as directed by standard protocols from Thermo fisher Scientific (Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). Expression was normalized to both GAPDH and ACTINB housekeeping genes before mRNA expression was normalized against the group indicated in each figure caption and quantified using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method (IL- 6: Mm01210732_g1, IL- 1 β : Mm00434228_m1, TNF- α : Mm00443258_m1, MMP13: Mm00439491_m1).

5.17. Histology. Stifles were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin and decalcified in Immunocal for 72 h (StatLab, McKinney, TX). All tissue handling for histopathology was performed in the Vanderbilt Translational Pathology Shared Resource by certified histotechnicians. Fixed tissues were routinely processed using a standard 8 h processing cycle of graded alcohols, xylenes, and paraffin wax, embedded, sectioned at 5 μ m, floated on a water bath, and mounted on positively charged glass slides. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was performed on the Gemini autostainer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA). Safranin O staining was performed by hand using a kit (StatLab). Stifle joints were evaluated by H&E and safranin O in at least 2 serial mid-frontal (coronal) sections. Each mouse knee underwent serial anterior coronal sections every 50 microns from point where there was disappearance of the patella to point where there was loss of femoral condyles. All these sections (>10 sections per joint) were assessed by the treatment-blinded pathologist from which 2 representative sections were selected and used for scoring. This

down-selection approach by a blinded third party was performed to reduce noise in scoring while appropriately representing each joint. This histopathologic section screening and scoring was conducted by a board-certified veterinary pathologist under treatment-blinded conditions.⁴² OARSI scores (0-6 semiquantitative scale) were provided for the medial tibial plateau and lateral tibial plateau.⁵³ Simultaneously, a more holistic scoring method, the Degenerative Joint Disease scale (DJD; 0-3 semiquantitative), was also used to supplement OARSI scoring of cartilage integrity with criteria appraising tissue inflammation, changes in bone morphology, and other signs of joint deterioration as defined in the included criteria (**Table. S1**).⁵³ All the scoring was done by a blinded pathologist, according to the criteria laid out in **Table. S1**. The most relevant features in the scoring were cartilage degeneration, meniscal metaplasia, subchondral osteosclerosis, synovial hyperplasia and inflammation, and osteophyte formation. For both analyses, the histopathologist had access to all sections from each joint and chose a section representative of the individual joint for scoring while still blinded to the treatment group.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project was partially supported by the European Research Council, under the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013)/ERC grant agreement no. 616695, and by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 754490 (COFUND-2018 “MINDED”) and grant agreement no. 872648 (RISE-2019 “MEPHOS”). The authors are grateful to the U.S. Department of Defense (DOD CDMRP OR130302), the National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship Program (NSF GRF #2016212929) (SKB), the NIGMS of the National Institutes of Health (T32GM007347) for support (JMC). The authors thank Dr Ennio Albanesi for his technical

support in conducting FACs experiments, Dr Benedetto Grimaldi for the Automated Cell Counters machine, the Staff of the Clean Room Facility, the Nikon Center, and the Material Characterization Facility of the Italian Institute of Technology. The authors also acknowledge the assistance of the Vanderbilt Translational Pathology Shared Resource (TPSR). TPSR is supported by NCI/NIH Cancer Center Support Grant 2P30 CA068485-14.

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FIGURES

Figure 1: Geometrical characterization of microPlates (μ PLs). **a.** Confocal microscopy and **b.** SEM image of an empty PVA template; **c.** Confocal microscopy image of a PVA template (red) filled with a PLGA/curcumin paste forming CURC- μ PLs (green/yellow); **d.** SEM image of individual μ PLs released from the PVA template. The lateral inset shows a magnified and tilted view of the μ PLs; **e.** Size distribution profile for μ PLs via a Multisizer Coulter Counter analysis; **f.** An optical-profilometer topographic image of a μ PL, where the red-level false coloring correlates with the local particle thickness. The plot on the right represents the cross-sectional profile of the μ PL.

Figure 2: Drug loading, release kinetics, and mechanical characterization of DEX-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs). **a.** DEX- μ PL fabrication yield and drug loading characterization; **b.** DEX release profile from μ PLs under the sink condition (4 L, red line) and Weibull function fitting (red line; 95% confidence band); **c.** DEX release profile from μ PLs under confined conditions (500 μ L green line; 95% confident band) and Weibull function fitting; **d.** Force-displacement curve for a flat punch indentation experiment on μ PLs (average curve and standard deviation). In the inset, a schematic of the experimental setup is provided; **e.** Mechanical damping of μ PLs upon cyclic loading (frequency 5 Hz) as a function of the force oscillation amplitude. In the inset, a schematic of the testing routine highlights the phase angle δ - dissipation parameter. Results are presented as the average \pm SD (n=3).

Figure 3: *In vitro* cytocompatibility and anti-inflammatory effect of DEX-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs). **a.** ATDC5 cell viability upon incubation with free DEX, empty- μ PLs, and DEX- μ PLs. Statistical analysis via one-way ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 5), is provided in the **Table. S3**; **b. – d.** Expression levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α for LPS stimulated ATDC5 cells. (**-LPS**: no LPS and no μ PLs; **+LPS**: LPS stimulation and no μ PLs; **DEX**: LPS stimulation and free DEX at 1 and 10 μ M; **DEX- μ PLs**: LPS treatment and DEX- μ PLs at 1 and 10 μ M). Results are presented as average \pm SD ($n \geq 4$). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.001$ and *** $p < 0.0001$ were considered statistically significant as compared to the control (+LPS); ## $p < 0.001$ and ### $p < 0.0001$ were considered statistically significant as compared to 1 μ M DEX and °° $p < 0.001$ and °°° $p < 0.0001$ were considered statistically significant as compared to 10 μ M DEX. Lack of statistically significant difference between groups is indicated on the graphs as NS. Multiple comparisons were performed using, as post hoc test, the Tukey's significant difference (HSD) test; **e.** a 30° tilted view of a SEM image of ATDC5 cells incubated with μ PLs. In the lateral inset, a magnified image shows cells interacting with μ PLs; **f.** false-color SEM image of a μ PL (red) deposited and not internalized over a layer of ATDC5 cells (green).

Figure 4: *In vivo* pharmacokinetic study of Cy5-conjugated microPlates (Cy5 - μ PLs) in a PTOA mouse model. **a.** Representative pharmacokinetic timecourse intravital images (skin on) and *ex-vivo* knee images (skin off) of Cy5- μ PLs injected intraarticularly into PTOA mouse knee joints (D-#, where # represents days after intraarticular injection). **b.** Intravital fraction of retention of Cy5- μ PLs plotted as mean + SEM. Note = The initial uptick in fluorescence within the joints in the first couple of hours after injection is a result of loss of fluorophore self-quenching, which occurs due to high density fluorophore conjugation onto the particles. **c.** Anatomically labelled sagittal section of a mouse knee joint 1 day after intraarticular injection showing the Cy5- μ PLs dispersed across the joint interacting and/or in close proximity to many different tissue types such as the cartilage, the infrapatellar fat pad and synovium, and the joint capsule. **d.** Confocal microscopy imaging performed 1 day after intraarticular injection showing Cy5- μ PLs located on top of the cartilage surface, near the cartilage/synovium interface, and the joint capsule. In all images, the scale bar = 100 μ m. **e.** Confocal microscopy imaging of Cy5- μ PLs within the mouse knee joint taken at different time points after intraarticular injection. TD = Transmission Detector. NT = No Treatment. For intravital imaging analysis, n = 4-24 limbs depending on the time point i.e., earlier time points had more animals included, and the sample size at the later timepoints was lower because some animals were taken down at earlier timepoints for *ex-vivo* and confocal microscopy analysis. For *ex-vivo* imaging analysis and confocal microscopy analysis, n = 2-4 limbs per time point.

a Intravital and Ex-vivo Knee Images of Cy5- μ PLs

b Intravital Pharmacokinetics of Cy5- μ PLs

c 1-D after Cy5- μ PLs Injection (10X)

d 1-D after Cy5- μ PLs Injection (20X)

e Cy5- μ PLs Surface Erosion and Loss of Shape and Structure over Time (20X)

Figure 5: Pro-inflammatory gene expression in a PTOA model mouse. **a.** Schematic of the loading fixture used in the mechanical loading of mouse knee joints to induce PTOA; **b.** mechanical loading regimen; **c.** *in vivo* expression of IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-6, and MMP-13 measured by TaqMan qPCR (for each treatment groups n=6, while for the healthy group n= 4). Statistical analysis via one-way ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 8), corrected for multiple comparisons by controlling the False Discovery Rate with a two-stage, step-up Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli method: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, while no significant differences are indicated on the graphs as NS. Full list of p-values is provided in the **Table. S4**.

Figure 6: Safranin-O staining of joint sections (OARSI scoring) and H&E staining of joint sections in a PTOA mouse model (DJD scoring). **a.** Representative safranin-O staining of the articular surface of the tibia and femur; inserts show areas of interest under increased magnification (top) and treatment-blinded histological scoring by OARSI standards (bottom) (for each treatment groups n=6, while for the healthy group n= 4). (Histology: Arrows – cartilage erosion, # - cartilage fissures, * - low safranin-O staining; Plotted Data: *p < 0.05, no significant differences are indicated on the graphs as NS). Statistical significance via one-way ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 8), corrected for multiple comparisons by controlling the False Discovery Rate with a two-stage, step-up Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli method; all images are matched in scale. **b.** H&E staining of PTOA joints showing a representative slide for each treatment group (Histology: # - mineralization, * - cellular infiltration and synovial membrane thickening); inserts show higher magnification images of synovial tissue (top) and Degenerative Joint Disease scoring of the joint histology by a treatment-blinded pathologist (bottom, * p < 0.05, while no significant differences are indicated on the graphs as NS); Statistical significance via one-way ANOVA (GraphPad Prism 8), corrected for multiple comparisons by controlling the False Discovery Rate with a two-stage, step-up Benjamini-Krieger-Yekutieli method, statistically; all images are matched in scale. In the lower magnification images, scale bar = 1 mm, while higher magnification images scale bar = 100 μm .

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Dexamethasone-loaded microPlates (DEX- μ PLs) lodged within the joints of a mouse with overload-induced osteoarthritis to reduce local inflammation, ameliorate cartilage degradation, and maintain normal joint structure.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

SHAPE-DEFINED MICROPLATES FOR THE SUSTAINED INTRAARTICULAR RELEASE OF DEXAMETHASONE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF OVERLOAD-INDUCED OSTEOARTHRITIS

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Number of pages: 13

Number of figures: 10

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SUPPORTING METHODS

Degenerative Joint Disease (DJD) scoring system. The Degenerative Joint Disease (DJD) scoring system was implemented to complement the OARSI scoring by assessing the joint holistically, scoring also for soft tissue and meniscal markers of PTOA advancement. ¹All scoring was done by a blinded pathologist, according to the criteria laid out in **Table S1**.

Severity Score	OARSI Scale	DJD Scale
0	Normal	Within normal limits: mild DJD as a feature of age-related change (e.g. articular cartilage attenuation and proteoglycan loss)
1	Loss of SO staining, thinning of articular cartilage; no defects	Moderate: articular cartilage degeneration with beginning of secondary pathology, including synovitis, joint capsule fibrosis, meniscal metaplasia
2	1 + fibrillation or pyknotic articular chondrocytes	Marked: metaplasia and/or fragmentation of one meniscus, osteophyte formation, synovitis/hyperplasia
3	2 + loss of articular cartilage <50% (e.g. erosion, flap, or callus)	Severe: metaplasia and/or fragmentation of both menisci, total loss of at least 1 articular surface (ebumation), osteophyte formation, advanced synovitis/hyperplasia
4	3 + fragmentation and fissuring in an area	N/A
5	4 + fragmentation and fissuring in >75% of the cartilage surface	N/A
6	Total loss of normal articular cartilage (end-stage)	N/A

Table S1. Safranin O scoring of tibial plateau cartilage degeneration and H&E scoring of overall stifle degenerative joint disease.

Water content into μ PLs. To estimate the water content in the μ PLs, a profilometric optical analysis was performed on samples before and after lyophilization. In both conditions, particle height and width were measured (**Table. S2**) ($n = 8$). The volume of the particles was calculated as $\text{Volume} = \text{Height} \times \text{Width}^2$. Prior lyophilization the average μ PL volume is $6680.30 \pm 198.40 \mu\text{m}^3$, whereas post lyophilization the μ PL volume is $6064.30 \pm 383.42 \mu\text{m}^3$. This results in $\sim 10\%$

difference in volume that should be ascribed to the water content. Notice that, given the small volume and mass of μ PLs, a total weight analysis prior and post lyophilization using high precision laboratory scales would require several tens of billions of μ PL, which is simply impracticable at the current state of development. Also, notice that the profilometric analysis was performed under regular ambient conditions, thus the lyophilized samples may have gained already water from the air umidity. As such the 10% volume difference should be considered as a conservative, first approximation on the water content in the μ PL. It is here also important to highlight that μ PL are different from conventional solid, spherical PLGA microparticles that have a more compact structure. This was demonstrated in a previous work by the authors ², where the ‘compactness’ of μ PL was increased by increasing the total mass of PLGA used during the synthesis process. Indeed, a reduction in degradation rate and drug release rate were documented as the mass of PLGA was increased. This has to be ascribed to a progressive reduction in water content in the μ PL with the increase in PLGA mass.

	Sample	Particles volume (μm^3)
Pre Lyophilization	μ PL 1	6570.38
	μ PL 2	6715.10
	μ PL 3	6757.17
	μ PL 4	6987.39
	μ PL 5	6432.72
	μ PL 6	6567.36
	μ PL 7	6498.02
	μ PL 8	6914.28
Post Lyophilization	μ PL 1	5853.12
	μ PL 2	5688.47
	μ PL 3	5553.17
	μ PL 4	6050.67
	μ PL 5	5890.31
	μ PL 6	6483.02
	μ PL 7	6485.71
	μ PL 8	6509.93

Table S2. microplate volumes prior and after lyophilization via optical profilometric analysis.

SUPPORTING RESULTS

Statistically significant differences for all the experimental groups of **Figure 3a** were assessed and listed in the **Table S3**. Significance corresponds to a p-value smaller than 0.05.

DEX Concentration (μM)	p values		
	Free DEX vs μPLs	Free DEX vs DEX- μPLs	μPLs vs DEX- μPLs
0.01	0.0012	0.0027	0.2739
0.50	0.6650	0.2169	0.2958
1	0.0611	0.2874	0.1340
10	0.0288	0.0508	0.7174
30	0.0002	0.0019	0.9644

Table S4. List of p-values for all the experimental groups of **Figure 5**.

Statistically significant differences for all the experimental groups of **Figure 5c** were assessed and listed in the **Table S4**. Significance corresponds to a p-value smaller than 0.05.

Gene	Healthy (yellow triangle) vs free DEX (blue circle)	Healthy (yellow triangle) vs Empty μ PL (green triangle)	Healthy (yellow triangle) vs DEX- μ PL (red square)	Saline (black cross) vs free DEX (blue circle)	Saline (black cross) vs Empty μ PL (green triangle)	Saline (black cross) vs DEX- μ PL (red square)	Free DEX (blue circle) vs Empty μ PL (green triangle)	Free DEX (blue circle) vs DEX- μ PL (red square)	Empty μ PL (green triangle) vs DEX- μ PL (red square)
IL-1β	0.0007	0.0015	0.0096	0.5658	0.2760	0.0013	0.5754	0.0024	0.0070
TNF-α	0.000061	0.0129	0.0013	0.7827	0.05889	0.0222	0.0612	0.0244	0.9559
IL-6	0.0006	0.0004	0.0220	0.34401	0.1909	0.0083	0.7281	0.0376	0.0506
MMP13	0.00005	0.00007	0.0044	0.3982	0.0086	0.0053	0.0268	0.0107	0.2614

Table S3. List of p-values for all the experimental groups of **Figure 5**.

Figure S1. A profilometric analysis of hydrated and lyophilized μ PLs. Representative cross-sectional profiles of μ PLs prior (red contour) and after (black contour) lyophilization.

Figure S2. Particle degradation. μ PLs degradation under physiological conditions, monitored over time using scanning electron microscopy.

Figure S3. Determination of live/dead cells after exposure to dexamethasone-loaded microPlates (DEX-μPLs). **a.** Percentage of live/dead cells after 24h exposure to different concentrations of free DEX, DEX-μPLs and empty μPLs using the trypan blue dye; **b.** Percentage of live/dead cells after 24h exposure to different concentrations of free DEX, DEX-μPLs and empty μPLs using FC with Propidium Iodide; **c.** Percentage of live/dead cells obtained with both techniques. Results are expressed as the average ± SD (n = 3).

Figure S4: *In vitro* gene expression effect of empty microPlates (μPLs). Expression levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1β, IL-6, and TNF-α in ATDC5 cells with or without LPS stimulation. Results are presented as average ± SD (n = 3). Multiple comparisons were performed using, as post hoc test, the Tukey's significant difference (HSD) test.

Figure S5. ATDC5 cells interaction with μ PLs. **a.** 3D and **b.** confocal microscopy analysis of ATDC5 cells incubated with CURC - μ PLs.

Figure S6. RAW 264.7 macrophages interacting with μ PLs. **a.** SEM images of RAW 264.7 macrophages incubated with μ PLs. The lateral inset shows a magnified image of cells surrounding the μ PL without internalizing it; **b.** false-color SEM image of μ PLs (red / orange) surrounded by RAW 264.7 macrophages (light beige).

Figure S7. Cy5- μ PL stability. The release of Cy5 molecules from Cy5- μ PLs is plotted over the full period of observation (30 days) at 37 °C. The direct conjugation of Cy5 molecules to the PLGA structure of μ PLs is extremely stable with a moderate loss less than 20% documented within the first hours only.

Figure S8. 20x Images of Cy5- μ PLs within the knee joint of a mouse model of PTOA at multiple time points. Cy5- μ PLs are seen in the joint for up to 30 days. Surface erosion and loss of shape and structure of microplates is evident over time. TD = Transmission Detector. In all images scale bar = 100 – μ m.

Figure S9. Magnified images of Cy5- μ PLs within the knee joint of a mouse model of PTOA at multiple time points. 20x Images zoomed in on Cy5- μ PLs within a mouse model of PTOA at days 1, 5, 25, and 30. Microplates are seen in the joint for up to 30 days with surface erosion evident by loss of fluorescence (heterogenous) in a significant number of individual Cy5- μ PLs at days 25 and 30 as compared to days 1 and 5. Cy5- μ PLs at days 1 and 5 have a consistent square shape and structure meanwhile Cy5- μ PLs at days 25 and 30 have lost this morphology. In all images on the right scale bar = 100 μ m. TD = Transmission Detector.

Figure S10. Cy5- μ PLs *ex-vivo* organ biodistribution in a mouse model of PTOA at multiple time points. Note that the fluorescent signal in the liver, which is seen even in the no-treatment (NT) mice, has to be ascribed to the autofluorescence resulting from a regular mouse diet. Paw autofluorescence can be ascribed to skin being left on the paw. (D-#, where # represents days after intra-articular injection). (N = 1-2 mice, 2-4 limbs per time point).

SUPPORTING REFERENCES

- (1) Aigner, T.; Söder, S. Histopathological Examination of Joint Degeneration: Typing, Grading and Staging of Osteoarthritis. *Der Pathologe* 2006, 27 (6), 431.
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